

HEREDITARY

HetERogeneous sEmantic Data integration for the guT-bRain interplaY

Deliverable 5.10

First evaluation challenge: report on the data, results, and integration with EOSC

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 5.10 presents the GUTBRAINIE evaluation challenge at CLEF 2025, advancing Information Extraction from biomedical literature on the gut-brain axis within the HEREDITARY project. The team behind the challenge developed an expert-curated dataset and annotation framework for biomedical IE tasks, benchmarked state-of-the-art NLP systems, and ensured FAIR compliance and EOSC integration.

The gut-brain axis is a rapidly emerging research area with profound implications for neurological and psychiatric disorders. Publications have grown exponentially from approximately 600 articles in 2020 to over 1,800 annually by 2025. The GUTBRAINIE task targeted the extraction of structured information from PubMed abstracts to address the challenge of systematic knowledge discovery from this rapidly expanding literature.

Dataset construction followed a rigorous multi-stage workflow. An initial PubMed retrieval yielded 1,647 unique articles. A diverse annotation team comprising 40 layperson annotators and 7 biomedical experts, supported by automated pre-annotation using GLiNER zero-shot NER models, systematically annotated documents. The resulting dataset comprises 1,600+ annotated documents stratified into four quality tiers. The gold-standard evaluation set contains 80 expert-annotated documents. The annotation schema identified 13 entity types and 17 fine-grained relation predicates with standardized URIs.

The challenge featured four subtasks of increasing complexity: Named Entity Recognition, Binary Tag-based Relation Extraction, Ternary Tag-based Relation Extraction, and Ternary Mention-based Relation Extraction.

International participation included 85 teams (17 submitted the final runs) from 29 countries submitting 391 runs total. Top-performing systems on NER achieved micro-averaged F1-scores above 0.84 using ensemble methods with fine-tuned biomedical transformers (PubMedBERT, BioBERT, BioLinkBERT). Relation extraction performance declined with task complexity: Binary Tag-based ($F1 \approx 0.69$), Ternary Tag-based ($F1 \approx 0.69$), and Ternary Mention-based ($F1 \approx 0.46$). Fine-tuned biomedical models substantially outperformed zero-shot LLM approaches, indicating that supervised domain-specific fine-tuning remains essential.

Following FAIR principles, the GutBrainIE dataset, annotation guidelines, and baseline system are publicly available on Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16845408) in multiple formats (JSON, CSV, TSV). Since Zenodo is part of the EOSC core infrastructure, these resources are automatically indexed and discoverable in EOSC by default. The dataset includes metadata on annotator expertise and quality, enabling reliability-aware training. EOSC integration provides the research community with open access to expert-curated biomedical IE benchmarks supporting reproducible research. The open-source baseline system and Codabench competitions enable community-driven advancement of biomedical NLP methods. This work directly supports HEREDITARY's objectives of semantic data integration and knowledge discovery.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Expanded form
BT-RE	Binary Tag-based Relation Extraction
CLEF	Conference and Labs of the Evaluation Forum
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
IAA	Inter-Annotator Agreement
IE	Information Extraction
LLM	Large Language Model
NER	Named Entity Recognition
NLP	Natural Language Processing
RE	Relation Extraction
TM-RE	Ternary Mention-based Relation Extraction
TT-RE	Ternary Tag-based Relation Extraction
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier

1 Introduction

Recent research trends in biomedicine increasingly link gut microbiota to neurological and psychiatric disorders like Parkinson's, Alzheimer's, Multiple Sclerosis, and mood disorders [Appleton, 2018; Carabotti et al., 2015; Cryan et al., 2020; Ghaisas et al., 2016]. As shown in Figure 1, PubMed publications on the gut-brain axis more than doubled from 2020 to 2025, increasing from 600 to over 1,800 articles annually. This poses a growing challenge for clinicians and researchers in staying updated, identifying, and interpreting relevant findings across unstructured scientific texts.

Figure 1: Annual rate of biomedical publications on PubMed related to the gut–brain axis, retrieved with the query “(gut-brain axis[Title/Abstract]) OR (gut brain axis[Title/Abstract])” on November 14, 2025. Blue bars highlight years with more than 1,000 records.

In response to this issue, the GUTBRAINIE task, inserted in the context of the BioASQ Lab [Nentidis et al., 2025a,b] at *Conference and Labs of the Evaluation Forum (CLEF) 2025*,¹ introduces a *Natural Language Processing (NLP)* challenge focused on extracting structured information from PubMed abstracts related to the gut-brain axis. GUTBRAINIE aims to foster the development and benchmarking of robust and effective *Information Extraction (IE)* systems capable of handling the linguistic complexity and conceptual specificity of gut-brain biomedical texts, thereby contributing to biomedical knowledge discovery and, in the long term, informed clinical decision-making.

In its first edition, GUTBRAINIE proposes four subtasks of increasing complexity:

- **Subtask 1 – Named Entity Recognition (NER):** participants are asked to identify and classify specific text spans (entity mentions) into one of the 13 predefined categories (e.g., *bacteria*, *chemical*, *microbiota*).
- **Subtask 2 – Binary Tag-based Relation Extraction (BT-RE):** participants are provided with a set of predefined relation types, each defined by a combination of compatible head and tail entities (e.g., *Chemical* → *Microbiome* via *Impact* or *Produced by*), and are asked to identify which entities are in relation within a document, without specifying the exact predicate or entity mentions involved.
- **Subtask 3 – Ternary Tag-based Relation Extraction (TT-RE):** this subtask extends BT-RE by requiring participants to predict the specific relation predicate connecting each head-tail entity pair.
- **Subtask 4 – Ternary Mention-based Relation Extraction (TM-RE):** this is the most challenging subtask, demanding to identify the exact entity mention involved in a relation and assign the correct relation predicate.

¹ <https://clef2025.clef-initiative.eu>

All subtasks target PubMed abstracts, building on a corpus of biomedical documents related to the gut-brain axis. Each document contains a title and abstract, both annotated with entity mentions and semantic relations. Specifically, the GUTBRAINIE dataset consists of over 1,600 annotated documents, split into Training, Development, and Test sets. An important feature of the dataset is its tiered annotation quality, organized as:

- **Platinum Annotations:** highest-quality annotations, expert-curated and internally reviewed;
- **Gold Annotations:** high-quality annotations and expert-curated;
- **Silver Annotations:** mid-quality annotations, curated by trained students under expert supervision;
- **Bronze Annotations:** automatically generated annotations with no manual correction.

In particular, the Development and Test sets contain only expert annotations (Platinum- and Gold-Standard Annotations).

Baseline results and participants' submissions are evaluated using standard IE metrics of Precision (P), Recall (R), and F1-score (F_1), assessed with both macro- and micro-averaging. Baseline systems have been shared with participants at the beginning of the challenge to provide reference performances.

This deliverable provides a comprehensive overview of the GUTBRAINIE task at CLEF 2025. Section 2 presents the subtasks and their structure; Section 3 details the end-to-end process employed for constructing the GUTBRAINIE dataset; Section 4 illustrates the released data and its statistics; Section 5 introduces participating teams, evaluation procedures, and baselines; Section 6 reports and discusses the results obtained by participating teams across subtasks, describing the systems, models, and approaches employed; finally, Section 7 draw conclusions.

2 Task Overview

This Section provides an overview of the four subtasks proposed in the first GUTBRAINIE edition. For each subtask, we detail the input training data, the expected output format, and the evaluation criteria, and provide illustrative examples of the corresponding annotations.

2.1 Subtask 1: *Named Entity Recognition (NER)*

The NER subtask focuses on classifying entity mentions into one of the 13 predefined categories. Participants were provided with PubMed abstracts related to the gut-brain axis and asked to identify specific text spans corresponding to one of the 13 predefined categories listed in Table 1.

Each entity mention consists of the following elements:

- **Location**, indicating whether the entity mention appears in the title or in the abstract.
- **Start and end indices**, denoting character offsets of the entity mention within the text.
- **Text span**, representing the actual string of text corresponding to the mention.
- **Label**, specifying the entity label assigned to the mention.

A predicted entity mention is considered correct only if all its fields exactly match an entry in the ground truth. Figure 2 shows an example of annotated entity mentions.

Figure 2: Example of annotated entity mentions for the NER subtask. The figure shows entities tagged in both the title and abstract of a PubMed article.

2.2 Subtask 2: Binary Tag-based Relation Extraction (BT-RE)

The BT-RE subtask is one of the three GUTBRAINIE subtasks dealing with *Relation Extraction (RE)*. In this subtask, participants have to determine which pairs of entities are in relation within a document, considering the set of relations defined in Table 2. Within BT-RE, participants are not required to predict a relation predicate. Therefore, a predicted relation for this subtask will be a pair (*subjectEntityLabel*; *objectEntityLabel*), where entity labels are taken from the ones reported in Table 1. Figure 3 shows an example of annotated binary relation.

Figure 3: Example of an annotated binary relation for the BT-RE subtask. The figure shows pairs of entities identified as being in relation within a PubMed article, without specifying the relation predicate and the entity mentions involved. Duplicated tag-based binary relations are merged into a single entry.

2.3 Subtask 3: Ternary Tag-based Relation Extraction (TT-RE)

The TT-RE subtask complements BT-RE by requiring participants to predict, along with the pair of entities in relation, the predicate of the relation holding among them. As in BT-RE, the set of relations to be considered is reported in Table 2. Predicted relations for TT-RE will be triples (*subjectEntityLabel*; *relationPredicate*; *objectEntityLabel*). Figure 4 shows an example of annotated ternary tag-based relation.

Figure 4: Example of an annotated ternary relation for the TT-RE subtask. The figure shows pairs of entities identified as being in relation within a PubMed article, specifying the relation predicate but not the entity mentions involved. Duplicated tag-based ternary relations are merged into a single entry.

2.4 Subtask 4: TM-RE

The TM-RE subtask is, among the three RE subtasks, the one most aligned with the standard NLP task of Relation Extraction [Bach and Badaskar, 2007]. Here, participants are required to identify the entity mentions involved in a relation, predict their entity labels, and specify the relation predicate that links them. Figure 5 shows an example of annotated entity mentions in a ternary mention-based relation.

Predicted relations for TM-RE will be tuples (*subjectEntityTextSpan*; *subjectEntityLabel*; *relationPredicate*; *objectEntityTextSpan*; *objectEntityLabel*).

3 Dataset Construction

The construction of the GUTBRAINIE dataset followed a four-stage workflow designed to ensure annotation quality and consistency.

- **Preparation phase**, involving the retrieval of documents from PubMed and the definition of the annotation schema and guidelines;
- **First annotation phase**, comprising expert review and correction of automatically generated NER pre-annotations and curation of relations;
- **Second annotation phase**, in which both experts and trained students annotated documents;

Figure 5: Example of an annotated ternary relation for the TM-RE subtask. The figure shows pairs of entities identified as being in relation within a PubMed article, specifying the relation predicate and the entity mentions involved.

- **Final curation phase**, which entails processing annotations to remove noise and ensure overall consistency and alignment. These annotations were then used to build the baseline system, which was subsequently employed to automatically annotate the remaining unannotated documents from the original retrieval.

Figure 6 details the entire workflow, showing the various steps involved in each phase. The remainder of this Section discusses in detail each phase and its associated steps.

Figure 6: The annotation workflow followed in the development of the GUTBRAINIE-2025 challenge.

3.1 Annotators Recruitment

Throughout the entire GUTBRAINIE annotation workflow, we decided to use an in-house team of annotators instead of external crowdworkers. This decision came from the specialized and intricate nature of the

gut-brain axis field, necessitating annotators with an adequate level of expertise and training. Furthermore, having internal annotators allows for regular feedback sessions, enhancing the consistency and quality of annotations. Our recruitment efforts resulted in a team composed of 40 layperson and 7 expert annotators. Layperson annotators were master's students enrolled in a terminology course and trained on the gut-brain axis terms and concepts. The group of experts consisted of computer scientists and terminologists, all with an academic background and prior experience in evaluation campaigns. Complementing these annotators, we involved external biomedical specialists from organizations working in the fields of brain disorders and gut microbiota. The involvement of multiple annotators with different expertise and backgrounds was intended to prevent the developed IE models from being biased towards the annotation style or task interpretation of a single individual, ensuring a balanced representation of annotation perspectives [Davani et al., 2022; Geva et al., 2019].

3.2 Preparation Phase

The preparation phase began with the retrieval of domain-specific documents from PubMed using two separate queries targeting the gut-brain axis, identified by external biomedical experts as formulations commonly used in systematic reviews:

- "gut microbiota" AND "Parkinson"
- "gut microbiota" AND "mental health"

Two retrieval rounds were conducted on May 9th and October 31st, 2024, resulting in 1662 documents. After filtering out duplicates and low-relevance documents from earlier publication years (2013-2020), the final collection included 1,647 unique documents.²

Following retrieval, we employed an iterative brainstorming approach for defining the annotation schema and guidelines. Initially, a representative subset of 100 PubMed abstracts was selected from the pool of retrieved documents and carefully analyzed by a focus group of expert annotators in collaboration with biomedical domain experts and terminologists, leading to the identification of a core set of domain-specific definitions. Based on these, we drafted a first annotation schema defining the entities and relations of interest. This schema was then refined by extending the analysis to cover the full set of retrieved documents through targeted sampling and preliminary pilot annotations. That allowed to filter out from the annotation schema entity types and relation predicates that were excessively underrepresented, resulting in the finalized structure illustrated in Figure 7, comprising 13 entity types and 17 fine-grained relation predicates.

Following the definition of the conceptual schema, we formalized the entity types by associating each of them with a unique URI pointing to a standardized concept in a biomedical reference resource, and by providing an accompanying explanation that clarifies its scope and semantic meaning. The 13 distinct entity types supported by GUTBRAINIE are listed in Table 1, while Table 2 reports the 17 relation predicates along with the corresponding valid head and tail entity types.

After these steps, the team of expert annotators defined a detailed set of annotation guidelines with the final goal of obtaining high-quality annotations that are consistent across different annotators and documents. Inspired by prior works on biomedical NLP dataset construction such as BioRED [Luo et al., 2022], BC5CDR [Li et al., 2016] and BioASQ-QA [Krithara et al., 2023], these guidelines detail the end-to-end annotation process to be followed for each document, including labeling rules, edge case handling, and examples of typical annotations and mistakes.³

²These retrieval queries differ from those used in Figure 1. The queries used in Figure 1 show the growth of the gut-brain axis literature over time, whereas the queries reported here were tailored to retrieve task-specific documents.

³The annotation guidelines are available at: https://hereditary.dei.unipd.it/challenges/gutbrainie/2025/files/GutBrainIE_2025_Annotation_Guidelines.pdf

Table 1: Overview of the 13 entity labels used in the GUTBRAINIE-2025 corpus, including their corresponding URIs and explanations.

Entity Label	URI	Explanation
Anatomical Location	NCIT_C13717	Named locations of or within the body.
Animal	NCIT_C14182	A non-human living organism that has membranous cell walls, requires oxygen and organic foods, and is capable of voluntary movement, as distinguished from a plant or mineral.
Biomedical Technique	NCIT_C15188	Research concerned with the application of biological and physiological principles to clinical medicine.
Bacteria	NCBITaxon_2	One of the three domains of life (the others being Eukarya and ARCHAEA), also called Eubacteria. They are unicellular prokaryotic microorganisms which generally possess rigid cell walls, multiply by cell division, and exhibit three principal forms: round or coccal, rodlike or bacillary, and spiral or spirochetal.
Chemical	CHEBI_59999	A chemical substance is a portion of matter of constant composition, composed of molecular entities of the same type or of different types. This category also includes metabolites, which in biochemistry are the intermediate or end product of metabolism, and neurotransmitters, which are endogenous compounds used to transmit information across the synapses.
Dietary Supplement	MESH_68019587	Products in capsule, tablet or liquid form that provide dietary ingredients, and that are intended to be taken by mouth to increase the intake of nutrients. Dietary supplements can include macronutrients, such as proteins, carbohydrates, and fats; and/or micronutrients, such as vitamins; minerals; and phytochemicals.
Disease, Disorder, or Finding (DDF)	NCIT_C7057	A condition that is relevant to human neoplasms and non-neoplastic disorders. This includes observations, test results, history and other concepts relevant to the characterization of human pathologic conditions.
Drug	CHEBI_23888	Any substance which when absorbed into a living organism may modify one or more of its functions. The term is generally accepted for a substance taken for a therapeutic purpose, but is also commonly used for abused substances.
Food	NCIT_C1949	A substance consumed by humans and animals for nutritional purpose.
Gene	SNOMEDCT_67261001	A functional unit of heredity which occupies a specific position on a particular chromosome and serves as the template for a product that contributes to a phenotype or a biological function.
Human	NCBITaxon_9606	Members of the species <i>Homo sapiens</i> .
Microbiome	OHMI_0000003	This term refers to the entire habitat, including the microorganisms (bacteria, archaea, lower and higher eukaryotes, and viruses), their genomes (i.e., genes), and the surrounding environmental conditions.
Statistical Technique	NCIT_C19044	A method of calculating, analyzing, or representing statistical data.

Following the definition of the annotation schema and guidelines and before starting the manual annotation phases, a hands-on training session was conducted. During this session, experts jointly annotated a set of abstracts for both entity mentions and relations while reviewing and refining the guidelines to ensure consistent interpretation and resolve any ambiguities early on. Two additional sessions were conducted with biomedical experts, following the same process and providing domain-specific feedback for further guidelines adjustments.

3.3 First Annotation Phase

Before starting the actual manual curation, we implemented and adopted an automatic annotation support strategy for entity mentions to reduce the manual effort required from annotators and accelerate the annotation process [Ganchev et al., 2007; Greinacher and Horn, 2018; Mikulová et al., 2023]. We began by selecting a representative sample of ten documents and asked two terminologists to manually annotate all entity mentions

Table 2: Overview of the relations used in the GUTBRAINIE-2025 challenge, expressed as head–predicate–tail triples.

Head Entity	Tail Entity	Predicate
Anatomical Location	Human Animal	Located in
Bacteria	Bacteria Chemical Drug	Interact
Bacteria	DDF	Influence
Bacteria	Gene	Change expression
Bacteria	Human Animal	Located in
Bacteria	Microbiome	Part of
Chemical	Anatomical Location Human Animal	Located in
Chemical	Chemical	Interact Part of
Chemical	Microbiome	Impact Produced by
Chemical Dietary Supplement Drug Food	Bacteria Microbiome	Impact
Chemical Dietary Supplement Food	DDF	Influence
Chemical Dietary Supplement Drug Food	Gene	Change expression
Chemical Dietary Supplement Drug Food	Human Animal	Administered
DDF	Anatomical Location	Strike
DDF	Bacteria Microbiome	Change abundance
DDF	Chemical	Interact
DDF	DDF	Affect Is a
DDF	Human Animal	Target
Drug	Chemical Drug	Interact
Drug	DDF	Change effect
Human Animal Microbiome	Biomedical Technique	Used by
Microbiome	Anatomical Location Human Animal	Located in
Microbiome	Gene	Change expression
Microbiome	DDF	Is linked to
Microbiome	Microbiome	Compared to

contained within them. We then selected a competitive zero-shot NER model–GLINER [Zaratiana et al., 2024a]–and systematically experimented with different pre-trained checkpoints, temperature values, and post-processing strategies, comparing the model’s predicted entities with the manually annotated ones. Based on

these experiments, we empirically selected the *NuNER Zero* checkpoint and adopted a temperature value of 0.8 to obtain a higher recall while accepting a moderate drop in precision, minimizing the number of entity mentions annotated by terminologists but missed by the model [Bogdanov et al., 2024]. Moreover, we defined a post-processing strategy that merged adjacent or overlapping entity mentions. When merged entities had different labels, we chose the one associated with the longest text span. Pre-annotation was limited to entities: we avoided pre-annotating relations since, in some preliminary experiments, we noticed that zero-shot RE models tended to introduce excessive noise, which risked biasing annotators and compromising annotation quality [Sanh et al., 2020]. To preliminarily assess the impact of these pre-annotations, we asked the same terminologists to annotate ten additional documents using the GLiNER-generated pre-annotations. Without pre-annotations, they needed approximately 30 minutes per document to fully annotate its entity mentions. With pre-annotations, the time dropped to 10-15 minutes, depending on the document's complexity, confirming the effectiveness of pre-annotations in reducing manual effort and speeding up the annotation process.

All pre-annotated documents were annotated with *MetaTron*,⁴ a free and publicly available web-based annotation platform [Irrera et al., 2024]. In this first annotation phase, only expert annotators were involved. Each of them was assigned 20 unique documents along with a shared set of 5 “honeypot documents”. The latter were introduced to compute *Inter-Annotator Agreement (IAA)*, enabling direct comparison of annotations across annotators and the assessment of their agreement and consistency. For this reason, annotators were informed that shared documents were included among those assigned but were not told which ones, to preserve unbiased agreement estimates. To avoid bias or information leakage, we instructed annotators not to consult with each other until all their annotations were completed [Alonso and Marchionini, 2019; Marchesin et al., 2024]. In computing IAA, two annotations were considered to be in agreement only if their text spans, labels, and predicates (in the case of relations) exactly matched. Using Fleiss' Kappa [Fleiss, 1971] and Mean Pairwise Cohen's Kappa [Cohen, 1960] as metrics, we observed strong agreement for NER (0.89 and 0.88, respectively), aligned with previous biomedical datasets such as BioRED [Luo et al., 2022] and NLM-Gene [Islamaj et al., 2021]. Agreement on RE was lower (0.43 for both metrics) but consistent with prior works involving complex relation annotation, reflecting the inherent challenges of a semantically difficult domain like the gut-brain axis [Kim et al., 2013].

To complement the IAA analysis, a subgroup of expert annotators manually revised all documents annotated during this phase. This step led to the correction or removal of 204 entities and 135 relations. For entities, roughly one-third of edits were due to incorrect text spans, another third to mislabeling, and the rest to overly generic mentions that violated annotation guidelines. For relations, about one-third were revised for incorrect directionality, another third for wrong predicate assignment, and the remainder for insufficient textual support. This review also allowed for the identification of issues in the annotation guidelines, which were refined accordingly. All annotations were then retroactively updated to align with the updated guidelines.

3.4 Second Annotation Phase

We started the second annotation phase by improving the quality and reliability of pre-annotated entity mentions by fine-tuning the GLiNER model on the final revised annotations from the first phase. We kept the pre-trained checkpoint and post-processing strategy fixed and varied the temperature values for fine-tuning and inference, with the honeypot documents held out from training and used as a validation set. Since fine-tuning allowed the model to obtain high recall even at lower temperatures, we empirically determined the optimal value as 0.5 for both fine-tuning and inference, as it provided a satisfactory recall while improving precision.

In this second phase, each expert annotator was assigned 40 new documents. Since expert annotators were already familiar with the schema and task and had demonstrated sufficient experience during the first

⁴<https://metatron.dei.unipd.it/>

phase, we decided not to include additional honeypot documents to assess their performance. In this second annotation phase we also introduced layperson annotators, each assigned with 24 documents divided into four batches. In each batch, one honeypot document previously annotated by experts was randomly inserted. Laypeople were required to annotate a minimum of one full batch, ensuring that each of them was labeling at least one honeypot document. As in the first phase with expert annotators, they were informed that shared documents were included but were not told which ones, encouraging accurate and unbiased annotations.

To assess the quality of layperson annotations, we computed Cohen's Kappa on their annotated honeypot documents against the reference version curated by experts [Cohen, 1960]. Agreement for NER was moderate and acceptable (0.50), indicating that with adequate training and supervision non-expert annotators can contribute reliable entity annotations. In contrast, RE agreement was low (0.17), largely due to the annotation of relations against the guidelines. This result also highlights the critical role that domain-specific expertise plays in annotating relations. To complement the assessment of layperson annotators, we reviewed their annotations and clustered them into groups A and B based on the overlap between their annotations and the adjudicated expert version. Group A included those whose annotations matched at least 65% of the expert-labeled entity mentions and 40% of the relations.

3.5 Final Curation Phase

After the end of the second annotation phase, expert annotators conducted a final review meeting to evaluate the second batch of annotated documents, addressing any unresolved issues and making corrections to ensure consistency across the full collection. Moreover, in this final curation phase we automatically annotated the remaining unlabelled documents from the original retrieval for entities and relations, aiming to expand the GUTBRAINIE corpora to better support large-scale training and weak supervision scenarios. For NER, we fine-tuned again the GLiNER model using the full set of expert-annotated data. For RE, we introduced ATLOP, a model leveraging adaptive thresholding and localized context pooling to effectively capture long-tail relations [Zhou et al., 2021]. This feature is critical for the GUTBRAINIE corpus, where various low-frequency relations play a significant role in accurately representing biomedical interactions. ATLOP was trained with expert annotations as primary supervision and student annotations as weak supervision. Although no manual revision was performed on this data, we applied a post-processing step to ensure adherence to the same schema and guidelines as the human-curated data.

4 Released Datasets

Once all the documents from the original retrieval were annotated, either manually or automatically, we organized them into four quality-based folds reflecting the reliability of the annotations and the level of expertise of the annotators involved:

1. **Platinum:** highest-quality annotations produced by experts during the first manual annotation phase and internally reviewed by a subgroup of them.
2. **Gold:** high-quality annotations created by experts during the second manual annotation phase, when they were already experienced and familiar with the schema and guidelines. For that reason, this fold maintains high reliability even if no subsequent revision has been performed.
3. **Silver:** Annotations of intermediate quality produced by layperson annotators (trained students) under expert supervision.

4. **Bronze:** automatically generated annotations using the baseline system. These were processed to ensure alignment with the annotation schema and guidelines, but no further manual correction or review was performed.

The training set includes all four quality folds. As for the Development and Test sets, they contain only expert annotations (Platinum and Gold), manually selected to ensure full coverage and representativeness of all entity types and relation predicates. The Test set is released without gold annotations to guarantee fair submissions during the evaluation of participants' submissions. Participants obtained their test-set scores by sending their system predictions to the organizers, who then computed the evaluation metrics and returned the results.

Each annotation is tagged with an anonymized annotator ID, with expert annotators identified as `expert [1-7]` and automatic annotations as `automatic`. Layperson annotators are identified as `student [A/B]`, depending on the reliability cluster to which they have been assigned.

This tiered annotation quality, along with annotator metadata, allows models to be trained or tuned by weighting or filtering annotations differently based on their reliability, supporting training strategies such as reliability-aware loss weighting [Guo and Yang, 2024; Ibrahim et al., 2020; Lin et al., 2019] and selective denoising [Alomar et al., 2023; Becker et al., 2005; Ghosh et al., 2023]. Table 3 shows the distribution of documents and annotations per fold.

Table 3: GUTBRAINIE-2025 dataset statistics.

Collection	No. Docs	No. Ents	Ents/Doc	No. Rels	Rels/Doc
Silver	499	15,275	30.61	10,616	21.27
Gold	208	5,192	24.96	1,994	9.59
Platinum	111	3,638	32.77	1,455	13.11
Dev	40	1,117	27.93	623	15.58
Test	40	1,237	30.92	777	19.42
Manual	898	26,459	29.46	15,465	17.22
Automatic (Bronze)	749	21,420	28.51	8,533	10.90
Overall	1,647	47,879	29.03	23,998	14.35

4.1 Dataset Format

Annotations are provided in JSON format. Each entry corresponds to a PubMed article, keyed by its PubMed ID (PMID), and contains the following fields:

- **Metadata:** Article-level information including:
 - *title, author, journal, year, abstract*;
 - *annotator_id*: one of `expert_1–expert_7`, `student_A`, `student_B`, or `distant` (automatically generated).
- **Entities:** An array of objects, each with:
 - *start, end*: character offsets of the text span associated to the entity mention;
 - *location*: “title” or “abstract”;

- *text_span*: the actual text span of the mention;
- *label*: the annotated entity label (such as *bacteria*, *microbiome*).
- **Relations**: An array of objects representing relations, each with:
 - *subject_start*, *subject_end*, *subject_location*, *subject_text_span*, *subject_label*: the subject entity mention;
 - *predicate*: the annotated relation predicate;
 - *object_start*, *object_end*, *object_location*, *object_text_span*, *object_label*: the object entity mention.
- **Binary Tag-based Relations**: Derived from the `Relations` array by extracting pairs `<subject_label, object_label>`, omitting relation predicate and mention-level details.
- **Ternary Tag-based Relations**: Extracted from the `Relations` array as triples `<subject_label, predicate, object_label>`, including relation predicate but leaving out mention-level details.
- **Ternary Mention-based Relations**: Extracted from the `Relations` array as mention-level tuples `<subject_text_span, subject_label, predicate, object_text_span, object_label>`. Information about the location of entity mentions in the text is neglected.

4.1.1 Alternative Dataset Formats

For convenience, each field above is also provided in both CSV and TSV formats:

- `metadata.csv` — `metadata.tsv`
- `entities.csv` — `entities.tsv`
- `relations.csv` — `relations.tsv`
- `binary_tag_relations.csv` — `binary_tag_relations.tsv`
- `ternary_tag_relations.csv` — `ternary_tag_relations.tsv`
- `ternary_mention_relations.csv` — `ternary_mention_relations.tsv`

CSV files use the pipe symbol (`|`) as a delimiter, while TSV files use the tab character (`\t`).

4.2 Zenodo Repository and EOSC Integration

The data described in this deliverable are publicly available according to the FAIR principles on Zenodo, at the link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16845408>. The repository provides the fully annotated documents for the training and development sets in three formats (JSON, CSV, TSV), the PDF document containing the annotation guidelines used in both annotation phases, and a ZIP folder with the complete implementation of the baseline system and the evaluation scripts for each of the four subtasks. For the test set, the Zenodo record includes only document metadata (title, abstract, author(s), year of publication, PubMed ID), but not the corresponding ground truth annotations. These are intentionally kept hidden to promote fair submissions and foster reproducibility. Systems' predictions can be evaluated on the test set through the established Codabench competitions (see Section 5.4), which run the official evaluation scripts against the ground truth and return performance scores while keeping the annotations hidden. Since Zenodo is part of the *European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)* core infrastructure, these resources are automatically indexed and retrievable within the EOSC ecosystem.

5 Participation and Evaluation

This Section provides a concise overview of the teams that participated in the GUTBRAINIE at CLEF 2025. A comprehensive description of the submitted systems can be found in Section 6 and in the participants' individual papers reported in Table 4.

Teams could participate in any of the four subtasks independently and submit up to 25 runs per subtask. Although 85 teams from 29 different countries registered for the challenge, the final number of teams submitting at least one run was 17, resulting in a total of 391 submitted runs. Among these, 15 teams also submitted a participant paper describing their methodologies, approaches, and systems. However, the discussion presented in Section 6 includes all 17 teams that submitted at least one run. Table 5 summarizes participation across the various subtasks.

The task began on February 3, 2025, with the release of the training and development sets. The test set was made available on April 28, and final submissions were due by May 10.

Table 4: Teams participating in GUTBRAINIE-2025, including their affiliations, countries, code repositories, and corresponding system description papers.

Team ID	Affiliation	Country	Repository	Paper
ata2425ds	University of Padua	Italy	link	NA
ataupd2425-gainer	University of Padua	Italy	link	[Piron and Di Nunzio, 2025]
ataupd2425-pam	University of Padua	Italy	link	[Pamio and Di Nunzio, 2025]
BIU-ONLP	Bar Ilan University	Israel	link	[Keinan et al., 2025]
DS@GT-bioasq-task6	NA	United States	link	[Mehta, 2025]
DS@GT-BioNER	NA	Canada	NA	NA
Graphwise-1	Graphwise	Bulgaria	Available upon request to the authors	[Datseris et al., 2025]
greenday	Stony Brook University	United States	link	[Gupta and Banerjee, 2025]
Gut-Instincts	Aalborg University	Denmark	link	[Andersen et al., 2025]
GutUZH	University of Zurich	Switzerland	link	[Han and Liu, 2025]
ICUE	University of Edinburgh	United Kingdom	link	[Lee et al., 2025]
lasigeBioTM	LASIGE, Faculdade de Ciências Universidade de Lisboa	Portugal	link	[Conceição et al., 2025]
LYX-DMIIIP-FDU	Fudan University	China	link	[Liu, 2025]
NLPatVCU	Virginia Commonwealth University	United States	link	[Taylor et al., 2025]
ONTUG	University of Technology, Graz; Ontotext, Bulgaria	Austria	NA	[Kantz et al., 2025] [Datseris et al., 2025]
Schemalink	Dept. of Computer Science University of Milan	Italy	link	NA
ToGS	University of Technology, Graz	Austria	link	[Kantz et al., 2025]

5.1 Participants

A total of 85 teams registered for the GUTBRAINIE @ CLEF 2025 task, of which 17 submitted at least one run and thus participated in the evaluation. In total, 391 runs were submitted: 101 for NER, 100 for BT-RE, and 95 each for TT-RE and TM-RE. Table 5 shows which tasks each team participated in and how many runs they submitted, while Table 4 reports their affiliations, countries of origin, and associated resources.

Table 5: Overview of the participating teams and submitted runs in GUTBRAINE-2025. Column “Runs” indicates the total number of runs presented by the team, while the other columns report the number of runs per subtask submitted.

Team ID	Runs	NER	BT-RE	TT-RE	TM-RE
ata2425ds	3	3	—	—	—
ataupd2425-gainer	33	3	12	9	9
ataupd2425-pam	37	10	9	9	9
BIU-ONLP	17	5	4	4	4
DS@GT-bioasq-task6	1	1	—	—	—
DS@GT-BioNER	3	3	—	—	—
Graphwise-1	68	23	15	15	15
greenday	1	1	—	—	—
Gut-Instincts	28	16	4	4	4
GutUZH	4	4	—	—	—
ICUE	95	23	24	24	24
lasigeBioTM	10	2	—	4	4
LYX-DMIIIP-FDU	4	1	1	1	1
NLPatVCU	40	5	15	10	10
ONTUG	4	—	2	1	1
Schemalink	4	1	1	1	1
ToGS	39	—	13	13	13

5.2 Evaluation Metrics

All four tasks are evaluated using standard IE metrics of Precision (P), Recall (R), and F1-score (F_1), with both macro- and micro-averaging. Let TP_ℓ , FP_ℓ , and FN_ℓ denote, respectively, the number of True Positives, False Positives, and False Negatives for label ℓ . We define the label set \mathcal{L} as:

- for subtask 1 (NER): the set of entity types;
- for subtask 2 (BT-RE): the set of pairs (*subject label, object label*);
- for subtasks 3 and 4 (TT-RE and TM-RE): the set of triples (*subject label, predicate, object label*).

The macro-averaged metrics are computed as:

$$P_{\text{macro}} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{L}|} \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} \frac{TP_\ell}{TP_\ell + FP_\ell}, \quad (1a)$$

$$R_{\text{macro}} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{L}|} \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} \frac{TP_\ell}{TP_\ell + FN_\ell}, \quad (1b)$$

$$F_{1,\text{macro}} = \frac{2 P_{\text{macro}} R_{\text{macro}}}{P_{\text{macro}} + R_{\text{macro}}}. \quad (1c)$$

The micro-averaged metrics aggregate counts before division:

$$P_{\text{micro}} = \frac{\sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} TP_\ell}{\sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} (TP_\ell + FP_\ell)}, \quad (2a)$$

$$R_{\text{micro}} = \frac{\sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} TP_\ell}{\sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} (TP_\ell + FN_\ell)}, \quad (2b)$$

$$F_{1,\text{micro}} = \frac{2 P_{\text{micro}} R_{\text{micro}}}{P_{\text{micro}} + R_{\text{micro}}}. \quad (2c)$$

For each subtask, the micro-averaged F1-score (Eq. 2c) is adopted as the reference metric for the final leaderboard.

5.3 Baseline

To support participants and provide a reference for performance evaluation, we developed a baseline system for all four GUTBRAINIE subtasks. This system is the same one used to generate the automatic annotations included in the Bronze fold of the training set (see Section 4).

The system consists of two independent modules: a NER module based on GLiNER [Zaratiána et al., 2024b], and a RE module based on ATLOP [Zhou et al., 2021]. The NER module employs GLiNER, a bidirectional transformer encoder trained for instruction-based named entity recognition [Zaratiána et al., 2024b]. We used the NuNERZero checkpoint [Bogdanov et al., 2024] and fine-tuned the model on the Platinum, Gold, and Silver portions of the training data, applying a confidence threshold of 0.6. After inference, we merged predicted entities having adjacent or overlapping spans. The RE module uses ATLOP, a document-level relation extraction model that employs localized context pooling and adaptive thresholding [Zhou et al., 2021]. ATLOP receives the document text and the entities predicted by the NER module and predicts relational triples within each document. The resulting relations are filtered to exclude any relation not supported by the GUTBRAINIE annotation schema (i.e., any relation not listed in Table 2). For fine-tuning, the Platinum, Gold, and Silver collections were used as manually annotated sets, while the Bronze collection was employed as distantly supervised data.

Table 6 reports, for each participating team, the number of submitted runs that surpassed the baseline system out of the total number of runs submitted for each subtask (considering the micro-averaged F_1 score as the reference metric).

The code implementing the baseline system is available at: https://zenodo.org/records/16845409/files/GutBrainIE_2025_Baseline.zip.

Table 6: Number of submitted runs surpassing the baseline system. For each team and subtask, the table reports the number of submitted runs that achieved a higher micro-averaged F1 score than the baseline system out of the total number of runs submitted.

Team ID	Total Runs	NER	BT-RE	TM-RE	TT-RE
ata2425ds	1/3 (33%)	1/3 (33%)	—	—	—
ataupd2425-gainer	0/33 (0%)	0/3 (0%)	0/12 (0%)	0/9 (0%)	0/9 (0%)
ataupd2425-pam	18/37 (49%)	0/10 (0%)	9/9 (100%)	9/9 (100%)	0/9 (0%)
BIU-ONLP	2/17 (12%)	0/5 (0%)	1/4 (25%)	1/4 (25%)	0/4 (0%)
DSGT-bioasq-task6	0/1 (0%)	0/1 (0%)	—	—	—
DSGT-BioNER	0/3 (0%)	0/3 (0%)	—	—	—
Graphwise-1	19/68 (28%)	1/23 (4%)	6/15 (40%)	6/15 (40%)	6/15 (40%)
greenday	1/1 (100%)	1/1 (100%)	—	—	—
Gut-Instincts	28/28 (100%)	16/16 (100%)	4/4 (100%)	4/4 (100%)	4/4 (100%)
GutUZH	4/4 (100%)	4/4 (100%)	—	—	—
ICUE	40/95 (42%)	9/23 (39%)	0/24 (0%)	19/24 (79%)	12/24 (50%)
lasigeBioTM	0/10 (0%)	0/2 (0%)	—	0/4 (0%)	0/4 (0%)
LYX-DMIP-FDU	1/4 (25%)	1/1 (100%)	0/1 (0%)	0/1 (0%)	1/1 (100%)
NLPatVCU	5/40 (13%)	5/5 (100%)	0/15 (0%)	0/10 (0%)	0/10 (0%)
ONTUG	3/4 (75%)	—	1/2 (50%)	1/1 (100%)	1/1 (100%)
Schemalink	0/4 (0%)	0/1 (0%)	0/1 (0%)	0/1 (0%)	0/1 (0%)
ToGS	0/39 (0%)	—	0/13 (0%)	0/13 (0%)	0/13 (0%)

5.4 Codabench Competitions

To foster comparability and reproducibility, we set up two Codabench competitions corresponding to the two tasks that we plan to keep proposing in future iterations of the GUTBRAINIE challenge at CLEF:

- Named Entity Recognition: <https://www.codabench.org/competitions/10830>
- Ternary Mention-based Relation Extraction: <https://www.codabench.org/competitions/10834>

These Codabench competitions enable participants to upload their system predictions for the Test set and automatically receive the evaluation results while keeping the gold annotations hidden. This ensures a fair evaluation pipeline, supporting reproducible benchmarking across different editions of GUTBRAINIE.

6 Results and Discussion

This Section presents and discusses the performances of participants' submitted systems for each subtask, based on the evaluation metrics described in Section 5.2. Discussion is organized into two subsections: Section 6.1 focuses on NER (subtask 1), while Section 6.4 covers RE (subtasks 2, 3, and 4). We do not include separate discussions for each RE subtask, as none of the participating teams implemented approaches specifically tailored to the Tag-based RE subtasks. Instead, all teams developed systems targeting TM-RE and then derived predictions for the other subtasks from these outputs. For each subtask, we report the leaderboard tables showing the best-performing run per team ranked by micro-averaged F_1 score. Complete scores for every submitted run can be found in the annex files.

6.1 Subtask 1 (NER) Results

The leaderboard for subtask 1 (NER) is reported in Table 7. Results for all submitted NER runs are shown in annex file 1.

Table 7: Performance metrics of each team's top run for NER. For each evaluation metric, the best result is in bold, the second-best is underlined.

Team ID	Run ID	System Desc	Macro-averaging			Micro-averaging		
			Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall	F1
GutUZH	2	AugEnsemble	0.7950	0.7736	0.7613	0.8384	0.8432	0.8408
Gut-Instincts	5eedev		0.7619	0.7813	<u>0.7591</u>	0.8286	0.8480	<u>0.8382</u>
NLPatVCU	ensemble1	ensemble1	<u>0.8139</u>	0.7161	0.7169	0.8255	0.8488	0.8370
ICUE	ensemble5	th10	0.8216	0.7451	0.7546	<u>0.8369</u>	0.8294	0.8331
LYX-DMIIIP-FDU	run1	EnsembleBERT	0.7605	0.7910	0.7347	0.8020	0.8513	0.8259
ata2425ds	trf	tranformer	0.7199	0.7546	0.7217	0.7914	0.8432	0.8164
greenday	1	llmner	0.7368	0.7682	0.7471	0.7956	0.8278	0.8114
Graphwise-1	13	NERWise	0.7691	0.7398	0.7185	0.8066	0.7955	0.8010
BASELINE	Organizers	NuNerZero-Finetuned	0.6883	0.7690	0.7047	0.7639	0.8238	0.7927
ataupd2425-gainer	ma	trainplatinumandgold	0.5808	0.5322	0.5281	0.8333	0.7397	0.7837
DS@GT-bioasq-task6	1	glinerbiomed	0.6342	<u>0.7849</u>	0.6872	0.7337	0.8197	0.7743
DS@GT-BioNER	run2	pubmedbert	0.6731	0.6497	0.6469	0.7783	0.7437	0.7606
ataupd2425-pam	3	biosyn-sapbert-bc2gn-12	0.6400	0.7435	0.6763	0.6809	0.7745	0.7247
Schemalink	1	SchemaBasedMultiPrompt	0.4813	0.5038	0.4650	0.5547	0.5659	0.5602
BIU-ONLP	3	3_gliner_large_bio-v0.1	0.4393	0.3585	0.3711	0.4916	0.4721	0.4816
lasigeBioTM	R1	BENTMistral	0.2206	0.1034	0.0863	0.3471	0.1964	0.2509

Most participating teams in the NER subtask adopted supervised fine-tuning or transformer-based models pre-trained on large-scale biomedical corpora, with the most employed ones being PubMedBERT [Gu et al., 2021], BioBERT [Lee et al., 2019], BioLinkBERT [Yasunaga et al., 2022], and ELECTRA [Alrowili and Shanker, 2021]. In addition to these, several teams employed GLiNER [Zaratiana et al., 2024b] fine-tuned on the training data. Ensemble approaches were widely utilized to improve effectiveness, often combining models trained with different data, seeds, and configurations.

While the majority of teams used the platinum, gold, and silver folds, a few also included the noisier bronze data, applying cleaning or re-weighting strategies. Some systems also incorporated additional knowledge from external corpora or pseudo-labeled texts to enhance training coverage.

A smaller number of teams experimented with prompt-based or zero-shot methods using Large Language Models (LLMs). These approaches avoided traditional supervised learning and relied on structured prompting and schema-guided extraction.

Overall, systems that combined strong biomedical backbones with fine-tuning and ensemble strategies tended to outperform others.

6.2 Subtask 2 (BT-RE) Results

Table 8 presents the leaderboard for subtask 2 (BT-RE), while annex file 2 reports the complete results for all BT-RE submitted runs.

Table 8: Performance metrics of each team's top run for BT-RE. For each evaluation metric, the best result is in bold, the second-best is underlined.

Team ID	Run ID	System Desc	Macro-averaging			Micro-averaging		
			Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall	F1
Gut-Instincts	6219eedev3re		0.5166	0.6315	0.5386	0.6304	0.7532	0.6864
ONTUG	union	ElectraCLEANR	0.4185	0.4073	0.4057	0.7121	0.6104	<u>0.6573</u>
Graphwise-1	104	AtlopOnto	0.4043	0.3748	0.3832	0.7418	0.5844	0.6538
ataupd2425-pam	A7	RE-BiomedNLP-3NoRel-1epoch	<u>0.4807</u>	0.6091	<u>0.4993</u>	0.5671	0.7316	0.6389
BIU-ONLP	4	RobertaLarge	0.4632	0.3379	0.3713	<u>0.7453</u>	0.5195	0.6122
BASELINE	Organizers	Atlop-Finetuned	0.4650	0.3564	0.3864	0.7584	0.4892	0.5947
LYX-DMIIP-FDU	run1	BioLinkBERT	0.3637	0.4269	0.3688	0.6168	0.5714	0.5933
NLPatVCU	C18	mixedCNNWLabModel4Preds	0.3975	<u>0.8419</u>	<u>0.5082</u>	0.4381	<u>0.8571</u>	0.5798
Schemalink	1	gpt4re	0.3758	<u>0.6573</u>	0.4421	0.4531	0.7532	0.5659
ataupd2425-gainer	bp	trainplatinumandgold	0.3171	0.3254	0.2968	0.6150	0.4978	0.5502
ICUE	run17	biolinkbertl_pp	0.3558	0.8790	0.4751	0.3894	0.9221	0.5476
ToGS	hermes8bragreorder	CLEANR	0.2211	0.1304	0.1451	0.5701	0.2641	0.3609

6.3 Subtask 3 (TT-RE) Results

Table 9 shows the subtask 3 (TT-RE) leaderboard, with full results for all submitted TT-RE results reported in annex file 3.

6.4 Subtask 4 (TM-RE) Results

The leaderboard for subtask 4 (TM-RE) is shown in Table 10. Results for all submitted TM-RE runs are reported in annex file 4.

Most participating teams approached RE as a supervised classification task, using fine-tuned biomedical transformers such as BioBERT [Lee et al., 2019], BioLinkBERT [Yasunaga et al., 2022], PubMedBERT [Gu

Table 9: Performance metrics of each team’s top run for TT-RE. For each evaluation metric, the best result is in bold, the second-best is underlined.

Team ID	Run ID	System Desc	Macro-averaging			Micro-averaging		
			Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall	F1
Gut-Instincts	6229eedev3re		0.4663	0.6445	0.5184	0.6280	0.7572	0.6866
ataupd2425-pam	B7	RE-BiomedNLP-3NoRel-1epoch	0.4409	0.5704	0.4694	0.5853	0.7202	0.6458
ONTUG	union	ElectraCLEANR	0.4254	0.4025	0.4058	0.7059	0.5926	0.6443
Graphwise-1	105	AtlopOnto	0.4119	0.3709	0.3840	0.7326	0.5638	0.6372
ICUE	run22	biolinkbertl_pp	0.4011	<u>0.7123</u>	<u>0.4879</u>	0.4974	<u>0.7860</u>	0.6093
BIU-ONLP	4	RobertaLarge	<u>0.4725</u>	0.3288	0.3630	<u>0.7362</u>	0.4938	0.5911
BASELINE	Organizers	Atlop-Finetuned	0.4729	0.3421	0.3745	0.7533	0.4650	0.5751
NLPatVCU	C19	mixedCNNWLabModel4Preds	0.3810	0.8005	0.4868	0.4362	0.8436	0.5750
LYX-DMIIIP-FDU	run1	BioLinkBERT	0.3625	0.4171	0.3549	0.5973	0.5432	0.5690
Schemalink	1	gpt4re	0.3756	<u>0.6592</u>	0.4437	0.4523	<u>0.7613</u>	0.5675
ataupd2425-gainer	td	trainplatinumandgold	0.3167	<u>0.2315</u>	0.2528	<u>0.7405</u>	0.3992	0.5187
ToGS	hermes8bragreorder	CLEANR	0.2261	0.1267	0.1414	0.5556	0.2469	0.3419
lasigeBioTM	R1	ConstParsing	0.0797	0.0622	0.0646	0.3929	0.0453	0.0812

Table 10: Performance metrics of each team’s top run for TM-RE. For each evaluation metric, the best result is in bold, the second-best is underlined.

Team ID	Run ID	System Desc	Macro-averaging			Micro-averaging		
			Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall	F1
Gut-Instincts	6239eedev3re		0.3310	0.4303	0.3497	0.4215	0.5147	0.4635
Graphwise-1	107	AtlopOnto	<u>0.3323</u>	0.2369	0.2603	0.4686	0.3097	<u>0.3729</u>
ICUE	run23	biolinkbertl_pp	0.2509	<u>0.4239</u>	0.2825	0.2858	0.5054	0.3651
LYX-DMIIIP-FDU	run1	BioLinkBERT	0.2106	0.2418	0.1990	0.3682	0.3257	0.3457
ONTUG	union	ElectraCLEANR	0.2589	0.2293	0.2266	0.3529	0.3231	0.3373
BASELINE	Organizers	Atlop-Finetuned	0.3514	0.1829	0.2123	0.4986	0.2453	0.3288
Schemalink	1	gpt4re	0.2265	0.4088	0.2546	0.1948	0.4665	0.2749
ataupd2425-pam	C7	RE-BiomedNLP-3NoRel-1epoch	0.1940	0.2764	0.1982	0.2278	0.3432	0.2738
ataupd2425-gainer	tms	trainplatinumandgold	0.2203	0.1384	0.1538	0.4272	0.1810	0.2542
NLPatVCU	C11	ensembleWLabModel4Preds	0.1522	0.5041	0.2163	0.1423	0.6005	0.2300
BIU-ONLP	4	RobertaLarge	0.1171	0.0854	0.0879	0.2339	0.1461	0.1799
ToGS	hermes3bloragreorder	CLEANR	0.0249	0.0180	0.0203	0.1702	0.0536	0.0815
lasigeBioTM	R1	ConstParsing	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

et al., 2021], and BioMedElectra [Alrowili and Shanker, 2021]. Entity pairs were detected via upstream NER modules, explicitly marked in input texts and used to generate relation-specific training instances.

Some teams tackled RE at the document level, incorporating sampling strategies (e.g., negative sampling, class-weighted losses) and architectural enhancements (e.g., query-based encoders, hypergraph neural networks) to better capture long-tail relations. Data augmentation, input filtering, and relation predicate-based constraints were also employed to refine candidate relation sets.

Ensemble techniques, including majority voting and model fusion, were used by several top-performing teams to improve systems’ effectiveness across the three RE subtasks.

Few teams experimented with prompt-based or zero-shot approaches using LLMs guided by structured templates or relation schemas, without any form of supervised training or fine-tuning.

Overall, the most effective submissions combined strong biomedical encoders with supervised fine-tuning and ensemble mechanisms.

7 Conclusions

GUTBRAINIE @ CLEF 2025 marked the first edition of a shared task dedicated to Information Extraction on the gut-brain axis, a research area of growing relevance in both neuroscience and microbiology.

This first edition saw 85 teams registering and 17 teams submitting a total of 395 runs. Participants tackled a diverse set of subtasks, from Named Entity Recognition to increasingly fine-grained Relation Extraction, with results highlighting the effectiveness of ensemble-based methods and biomedical transformers fine-tuned on domain-specific data and the relative immaturity of *Large Language Model (LLM)*-based approaches for biomedical IE.

The released dataset, including over 1,600 annotated PubMed abstracts stratified into annotation quality tiers, represents a valuable resource for training and evaluating biomedical NLP systems. Moreover, the defined evaluation metrics, baseline system, and Codabench competitions make GUTBRAINIE a solid biomedical IE benchmark that supports fair comparison and reproducible results. To promote the use of the GUTBRAINIE dataset and ensure transparency and alignment with the FAIR principles, both the data and the annotation guidelines are publicly released on Zenodo.

In future iterations of this shared task we plan to further improve the overall quality of the dataset by manually reviewing and annotating the current Bronze fold, currently composed of fully automatic annotations. We also aim to extend the task by incorporating entity linking, thus enabling the inclusion of two additional subtasks: entity linking itself and concept-level Relation Extraction, complementing the actual mention-level formulation. Finally, we intend to broaden the scope of the dataset by retrieving and annotating documents related to other major neurological diseases, including Alzheimer's, Multiple Sclerosis, and Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis.

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Annexes

Number	Name
1	Performance metrics of each team's submitted runs for NER
2	Performance metrics of each team's submitted runs for BT-RE
3	Performance metrics of each team's submitted runs for TT-RE
4	Performance metrics of each team's submitted runs for TM-RE